

D8.2 – Ethics requirements

Consorzio Italbiotec

Co-funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union (Grant n° .101113011) Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document control sheet

Project **BIN2BEAN** – Boosting the market deployment of safe, effective and sustainable innovations for soil improvement from bio-waste, towards regenerative soil systems

Topic identifier	Horizon-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-10
Grant Agreement N°	101113011
Coordinator	Consorzio ITALBIOTEC
Work package N°	8
Work package title	Project Management
Work package leader	Consorzio Italbiotec
Document title	D8.2 – Ethics Requirements
Lead Beneficiary	Consorzio Italbiotec
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Authors	Sara Daniotti
Contributors	Mary Christopoulou (EGL), Sven Robert Ganschow (SRH), Willie van der Broek (AMS)
Reviewer(s)	Liesbeth de Schutter, Joana Wensing (WU-UEC)
Due date	29/02/2024
Submission date	29/02/2024

Document history

Version, Date	Description
V1, 29/01/2024	First version
V2, 23/02/2024	Second version implementing the reviewer's comments
V3, 29/02/2024	Final version revised by partners implementing the last changes from the LLs

Project partners

Contacts

Sara Daniotti (Project coordinator):
sara.daniotti@italbiotec.it

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1 General ethics considerations.....	6
1.2 Relevant EU and national guidelines and legislations on ethics.....	7
2. Ethics requirements regarding the involvement of humans.....	9
2.1 Research activities involving humans.....	9
2.2 Research participants.....	9
2.3 Criteria that will be used to recruit research participants.....	9
2.4 Local ethics committee in LLs.....	10
3. Ethics requirements regarding the handling of personal data.....	12
4. Monitoring of the ethical considerations.....	13
Annex 1 – Informed consent template.....	14
Annex 2 – Declaration of GDPR compliance.....	16
Annex 3 – Additional documents provided by LLs.....	17
AMS GDPR procedure details.....	17

List of tables

Table 1. Relevant national and other local regulations on ethics.....	8
---	---

List of Acronyms

DPO – Data Protection Officer

DNSH – Do Not Significant Harm

EC – European Commission

GA – Grant Agreement

GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation

LL – Living Labs

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The present document, developed within WP8 – Project Management, summarizes the potential ethical issues that may arise when carrying out BIN2BEAN activities and the measures and actions put in place to prevent, remedy and monitor them.

Indeed, the BIN2BEAN partners commit to carefully consider in its own methodology ethics and compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations and declarations both at EU and national/local level. Despite not expecting any potentially critical ethical implications of the research results, this document mainly addresses the potential ethical concerns related to the involvement of humans and the handling of personal data. The "Do Not Significant Harm" principle is also addressed, ensuring that soil improvers will not have any negative impacts on environment, health and safety.

As the activities involving human participants will be carried out in the Living Labs, the present document particularly focuses on the strategies that are followed in the organizations of the LL leaders.

1. Introduction

Acknowledging the crucial role of local policymakers in the development of local circular economy plans, the main objective of BIN2BEAN is to help EU cities meet EU targets and objectives in their transition to healthy soils and soil regenerative systems, by optimising bio-waste recycling into soil improvers.

In the context of Work Package 8 – Project Management of the BIN2BEAN project, the present deliverable aims to describe the project ethics requirements, ensuring that the project activities are conducted in compliance with fundamental ethical principles and laws. In particular, the deliverable describes any potential ethical implication of the BIN2BEAN project, how ethics principles are handled within the three project Living Labs and the measures put in place to prevent, mitigated and monitor these potential issues.

1.1 General ethics considerations

BIN2BEAN does not expect any potentially critical ethical implications of the research results. However, aimed at establishing a participative approach with cities and local stakeholders involved in the bio-waste collection and valorization, social studies and their methodologies (questionnaires, interviews, workshops) are at the hearth of the BIN2BEAN methodology together with the need of involving stakeholders in different aspects of the project (e.g. Stakeholder Forum, LL participants). This requirement raises the needs to apply ethical principles and comply with relevant legislations related to the handling and protection of personal data that may be collected in the process, as well as concerning the rights and interests of the participants and different stakeholder groups.

The methods to involve humans in the project, the detailed activities in which they will be involved as well as the timing and interest for the project are described in the relevant tasks and WP of the Grant Agreement.

The BIN2BEAN consortium and its partners are committed to comply with ethical principles and relevant legislations and declarations both at European, national and partner level (see Paragraph 1.2).

HANDLING OF HUMAN DATA – Different groups of stakeholders will voluntarily engage in the Living Lab activities of the project, including participation in questionnaires, interviews, workshops, sight visits etc. In the Living Lab contexts, participants will be asked to share their knowledge and information regarding the local challenges, but only after participants have been informed on the aims, methods and implications of the activity. Since the social studies will be carried out within the LLs, each LL leader will ask the participants for a written consent that includes a statement that the participants have understood the information and activity. Furthermore, Bin2Bean partners will ask for an ethical approval to its local committee, following its general procedure, in advance of the activity. Given the

relevance of this topic for the BIN2BEAN activities, ethics requirements regarding the involvement of humans are described in Paragraph 2.

HANDLING OF PERSONAL DATA - Each partner is asked to comply with EU and (if applicable) national legislations in order to fully ensure the protection of personal data, that will be collected during social studies, project communication activities and day-to-day management activities carried out during the project. In this respect, each partner received a declaration of GDPR compliance to be signed by their Data Protection Officer (DPO). Paragraph 3 described the ethics requirements regarding the handling of personal data while D8.1 – Data Management Plan will provide details on how the data will be managed.

ENVIRONMENT, HEALTH AND SAFETY - The project fully complies with the “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle. Indeed, as soil improvers will have been carefully studied in equipped laboratories under safe conditions for the environment and human health before their application in the environment, no major negative impacts are foreseen when they will be tested on the soil (WP3). The improved evaluation framework developed by the project will also ensure that only soilutions with a higher safety profile will be selected. The purpose of the testing phase, indeed, will be to measure the efficiency of those improvers, rather than the safety as this parameter will be already assessed in equipped laboratories in order to reduce any major negative impact on the environmental and human health. In the unforeseen case that measures are needed to mitigate environmental harm in the frame of the project activities, the present deliverable will be updated with such procedures.

1.2 Relevant EU and national guidelines and legislations on ethics

In line with article 14.1 of the Grant Agreement, the project will “*be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles*”. Furthermore, for any applicable ethics issue, the guidance provided in the [European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines](#) will be rigorously followed.

BIN2BEAN methodologies and activities will comply with EU and international legislations on ethics, including, but not limited to, the following:

- the [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#) and the [European Convention on Human Rights \(ECHR\) and its Protocols](#) with a particular attention on the “third generation” fundamental rights, including data protection, guarantees on bioethics and transparent administration.
- the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) which outlines the fundamental principles of research integrity: *reliability, honesty, respect and accountability*.

- International laws such as the UN Declaration of Human Rights, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD) and the Nuremberg Code;
- Declarations and laws applying to the biomedical and behavioural research on humans, including the Helsinki Declaration and the Belmont Report. These documents indeed emphasize the need to protect participants and uphold ethical standards in behavioral research, including the importance of informed consent, benefits and risks assessment, and respect for individuals and the three fundamental ethical principles to be followed when conducting such researches: respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

Furthermore, each partner is expected to comply with any national legislation and other regulations within its organisation. Below, a summary of the main local regulations per country is reported.

Table 1. Relevant national and other local regulations on ethics

COUNTRY	RELEVANT REGULATIONS
ITALY	Guidelines for Research Integrity, CNR 2019
	Ethical Charter on Social Sciences and Humanities Research, CNR, adopted 16-03-2017
	Informed Consent in Scientific Research: Ethical Toolkit, approved 23-11-2017
GERMANY	Code of Deontology ("Arztliche Berufsordnung")
	The National Council for Ethics ("Deutscher Ethikrat"), as established by legislation of the " Deutscher Bundestag " on April 26, 2007 which may give recommendations which are not binding
	Central Ethics Committee of the German Medical Association which gives opinions on general ethical issues
GREECE	National Center of Social Research https://www.ekke.gr/en/centre/privacy_policy
	National Documentation Centre https://www.ekt.gr/en EU GDPR regulations https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/dealing-with-customers/data-protection/data-protection-gdpr/index_el.htm
	Code of Ethics of the Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign policy https://www.eliamep.gr/en/codeofethics/
FINLAND	The Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK, tenk.fi/en
THE NETHERLANDS	Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
FRANCE	Research Code, Articles L211-1 à L211-2 "Research Ethics"

2. Ethics requirements regarding the involvement of humans

2.1 Research activities involving humans

For its activities, BIN2BEAN will gather information from stakeholders through quantitative and qualitative methods (e.g. participatory modelling, workshops, questionnaires and interviews). Furthermore, local, regional and EU stakeholders are expected to participate all along the project (e.g., workshops, interviews, events, multi-actor Stakeholder Forum) and to contribute to the discussion and potential solutions for current barriers regarding bio-waste management (including collection), soil health issues and related needs for soil improvers, economic data and stakeholder perspectives, and will share their experience and knowledge through formalized feedback loops.

BIN2BEAN research activities will not involve any physical intervention on the study participants, including invasive techniques (e.g. collection of human cells or tissues, surgical or medical interventions, invasive studies on the brain, ...) and the collection of biological samples from humans.

2.2 Research participants

Stakeholders that will be engaged in the project can be identified as:

- a) Representatives of cities and municipalities
- b) Bio-waste producers including food manufacturers, food services and supermarkets
- c) Soil improvers producers and industries
- d) Local community initiatives on circular biowaste recycling
- e) Collection, transport and valorisation actors
- f) Research community and centers, mainly RTOs in bioeconomy, agriculture, toxicology, eco-toxicology, LCIA
- g) Farming communities including cooperatives, advisors, and individual farmers
- h) Households and citizens, also through the involvement of associations and NGOs
- i) Representatives of other projects and international networks
- j) Financial institution such as private entities, foundations and associations

BIN2BEAN research activities will not be conducted on/with persons unable to give informed consent, patients, children or any other sensitive groups.

2.3 Criteria that will be used to recruit research participants

Stakeholders' engagement will be **100% voluntary**; therefore, potential participants will not be pressured, cajoled, coerced into taking part in the project activities. They

will be free to choose whether to begin the study or, if they have already started, complete it or opt out without any consequences.

Furthermore, with an **informed consent** (the template for the informed consent is shown in Annex 1), potential participants will receive adequate information about the purpose, modalities, possible risks and benefits of the study, the type of personal data that will be collected and the purpose of collection before participating in the study in order to be able to make a choice about whether or not to be involved in the activity and share their personal data. This informed consent will be given either physically at events or workshops or via digital channels. The participants will be asked to read, fill and sign the consent forms, declaring they have read and understood the information received. A copy of those electronic documents will be stored on the data management storage system.

Finally, the project is committed to **avoid any form of discrimination**: persons of all genders and backgrounds, regardless their racial, ethnic, cultural and educational backgrounds, will be involved in the project activities.

2.4 Local ethics committee in LLs

Research activities involving humans as described in the paragraphs above will be carried out in the 3 project LLs (in Amsterdam, Egaleo and Hamburg). When carrying out these activities, LL leaders and/or the involved research partner will be responsible for ensuring that any survey, interview or other type of research that involves human within their LL is in line with the ethical standards provided in this document and the ethics procedures implemented internally with each LL leaders and/or partner organization as described below.

2.4.1 Living Lab Egaleo - EGL

Every sensitive and personal data that will be collected from participants and every document that will be administered to stakeholders involving the collection of sensitive and personal data will have to be approved by the Ethics Committee of EGL. The Municipality of Egaleo has a GDPR committee which has already initiated the procedures regarding consent for stakeholders that will participate in the Living Lab as well as the other actions of the project. The Ethics Committee is comprised of employees at the Municipality of Egaleo. Approval has already been given to begin the procedures with surveys or any other procedure that has to do with data collection. The approval document is reported in Annex 3.

2.4.2 Living Lab Amsterdam – AMS

The research within the Amsterdam Living Lab is coordinated by *AMS Institute* and executed by Bin2Bean partner Wageningen University, and Bin2Bean partner Wageningen Research. Both organizations have a common ethics committee installed for which both organizations bear (co)-responsibility. This so called WUR-REC team (Research Ethics Committee) evaluates the ethical aspects of a research, experimental or data collection activities and can be contacted at:

[WUR Research Ethics Committee - Review research ethics](#)

[WUR Information on ethical approval for non-medical research activities with human participants](#)

The REC evaluates the ethical aspects of a research, experiment or data collection activity prior to the planned activity. The AMS Institute management approved to rely on the WUR ethical and privacy guidelines. The AMS Institute will monitor the ethical procedures during the Bin2Bean project. More details on the GDPR procedures implemented in AMS, based on the REC recommendations, can be found in Annex 3. This procedure may be changed during the duration of the project if new recommendations for the REC and the AMS management emerge. In this case, the present document will be updated.

2.4.3 Living Lab Hamburg – SRH

Stadtreinigung Hamburg relies on strict internal ethical procedures that have been implemented and adopted since many years, that replaces the need to ask additional approvals from an ethical committee. By following this existing procedure that was approved by an Ethical Committee when implementing additional research activities on humans or other activities that are related to ethical issues, this research is not required to be approved again. The existing procedure covers all the ethics requirements as described below:

- A) The Unternehmensleitlinien (company guidelines reported in Annex 3) include all of these ethical standards. The contents of this document must be read and remain aware by every employee of SRH. These rules have to be respected in all activities of course.
- B) Every activity of SRH, that concerns public relations (publications, newspaper-articles, internet, image campaigns, social media, official statements to local authority, customer surveys etc.) must be released by the staff department communication. In case of need the equal opportunities officers, the staff advisor, the concern revision, the data protection officer or other representatives or departments have to be involved in before.
- C) All letters leaving the SRH have to be signed by two persons of different personal levels. The respect of all standards of the ethics requirements are reached by this way. That includes the published documents concerning the BIN2BEAN-project as well.
- D) SRH works following the rules of Hamburg Governance Codex [HCGK \(hamburg.de\)](#) based on DIN ISO 19600/ new: DIN ISO 37301 (Compliance management system certification, [ISO 37301 Compliance-Managementsystem-Zertifizierung | DE | TÜV Rheinland \(tuv.com\)](#)). SRH has a

well-developed compliance system. Concerning the releases and surveys of the BIN2BEAN-project there will be a final check by the representative of compliance, organized by the project management of the SRH. This finally certifies the ethics requirements.

- E) As an addition there is to mention, that SRH has reached the testate zur "Gemeinwohl-Ökonomie" (economy for common good) as first communal enterprise in Germany. It is tested by an external audit.

For any inquiries or complaints regarding the ethical aspects at SRH, including asking for a translation of the company guidelines, it is possible to contact the Compliance, Qualitätsmanagement und Organisation manager at:

Stadtreinigung Hamburg (SRH)
Compliance, Qualitätsmanagement und Organisation (Q-10), Beauftragter
für Compliance und Qualitätsmanagement
Schnackenburgallee 46, 22525 Hamburg, Germany
E-Mail: compliance@stadtreinigung.hamburg

3. Ethics requirements regarding the handling of personal data

Several activities within the project implies personal data collection and processing, mainly contact information to communicate with research participants, receive feedback and implement the follow-up of project activities. Therefore, as part of the engagement on ethics, the BIN2BEAN consortium has been committed to ensure that personal data collected during the project, regardless of the method by which they are collected, will be duly managed, protected and not shared with third parties in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679) as well as specific regulations in the country where they operate. Each partner is held responsible for the fulfillment of all legal and ethical requirements in its country. For this reason, all partners received a declaration of GDPR compliance (the template is reported in Annex 2) to be signed by their Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a designated representative, confirming that all personal data collection and processing in the research design of the BIN2BEAN project will be carried out according to thae EU and (if applicable) national legislation and organisational requirements. The signed declarations are made available upon request.

For research activities involving humans, as part of the informed consent (see Annex 1), potential participants will be made aware of the kind of information that will be collected and processed and will be asked for the consent to the lawful processing of personal data. The project will ensure to avoid any intentional or unintentional use

of information that can bring harm to any participants or being misused in other contexts.

More details on personal data and sensible information's collection, storage and use of this data are explained in the Data Management Plan (D8.1).

4. Monitoring of the ethical considerations

The ethical standards and principles of the project activities will be monitored throughout the entire project durations by the project coordinator, ITB, with the support of the project partners, mainly the LL Leaders. Ethical implications will be discussed during each consortium meeting with the aim of analysing past and future activities from an ethics point of view, identifying any unforeseen ethic issues and discussing about mitigation measures for the risks associated with those unforeseen issues. In case this will be discussed and implemented, the present deliverable will be updated with the new procedure and ethical considerations. In particular, if needed, based on the feedback received by partners when implementing their activities with humans and by the stakeholders involved in these activities, the opportunity to update the ethical guidelines provided in this deliverable will be discussed together with the LL. One of the main points of attention will be the ethical issues related with environment, health and safety and, in particular, the unforeseen case that measures are needed to mitigate environmental and/or social harm in the frame of the project activities, although at the present moment no major negative impacts are foreseen in relation to the testing of soil improvers.

Finally, in relation to the funnel approach implemented to select the solutions in each LL, the project partners will pay attention to the ethical implications of their role as process managers ensuring that all stakeholders' rights are respected and that the process is carried out equally and impartially based on objectives criteria.

Annex 1 – Informed consent template

INSTRUCTIONS

The following template includes an overview of the baseline elements that must be included in the informed consent for every BIN2BEAN activities involving humans. This template should be adapted to the specific activity for which the informed consent is required. Translation of the template in the local language is strongly recommended.

Specific template used in BIN2BEAN organisations as part of their usual recruitment procedures that have been approved by an Ethical Committee before the activities take place can be accepted as well. The template can also be modified in its shape and formatting provided that all the baseline information reported below are contained.

The informed consent must be provided to potential participants in paper or electronic form (depending on how the study is conducted) before the activity takes place.

The project logo and the acknowledgement of funding must be always included in the template.

INFORMED CONSENT FOR [insert here the title of the activity]

Information about the project

[Insert a short description of the project such as the following] Bin2Bean (Boosting the market deployment of safe, effective and sustainable innovations for soil improvement from bio-waste, towards regenerative soil systems) is a Horizon Europe research project, funded by the European Commission, which aims to support cities, countries and regions in their transition to regenerative soil systems by promoting safe, effective and sustainable innovations for soil improvement from bio-waste.

Bin2Bean notably aims to support territories in achieving the following EU targets:

- recycle 65% of EU municipal waste by 2035 (new Waste Framework Directive - Directive 2018/851)
- cap waste landfilled at 10% of total municipal waste (Landfill's Directive - Directive 2018/850)

Partner carrying out the study

This study is carried out by [Insert the full name and short name of your organization], established in [insert the country you are based in] as part of its activities as a beneficiary of the BIN2BEAN project.

Purpose of the study

BIN2BEAN involves in its methodology different groups of stakeholders with the aim to better understand current barriers and to contribute to potential solutions regarding bio-waste management (including collection), soil health issues and related needs for soil improvers, economic feasibility and circular community values, and will build and share its experience and knowledge in a participatory co-production approach.

In particular, the activities you are about to participate in / the questionnaire you are filling in aims to [Describe the activity and its aim and what the participant will be asked to do]

Participation

Your participation in this activity is voluntary. If you decide to take part in this study, you have the right to terminate your participation at any time without any negative consequences or penalties. You are free to decline to answer any particular questions for any reasons.

Before making a decision, if you have any doubts about the purpose of the research or the data collected or for any complaints, you can contact the researchers for further clarifications.

Confidentiality

You may be asked to provide your contact details (such as your name and email) which will be used for follow-up if you are interested in any further contacts [if relevant, add other personal data that will be collected]. The results of this research may be used for scientific, communication and reporting purposes and may be published. [Choose the most relevant option] However, personal information will not be published, and anonymity and confidentiality of the data will be guaranteed at every stage of the research. [OR] For these purposes (e.g. in public report), information you share may be quoted. Nevertheless, you have the right to authorize the sharing of such information or ask to be anonymized. If you ask to be anonymized, you will not be identified, and confidentiality of your personal information will be guaranteed at any stage of the research.

All data will be treated in full compliance with European and national legislation on data protection including GDPR regulation (n. 2016/679).

At any point, you can ask to have your contact details and personal data to be removed by contacting [insert here the contact of the DPO of the organization managing and storing the data].

Contact details

[Insert here the contact details of the researchers that can be contacted for the above-mentioned purposes]

By [choose the correct option based on the type of activity] signing this document/going on with the questionnaire, you declare the following:

- I have read and understood all the information above
- I have voluntarily decided to participate in this research and I am aware that I can withdraw at any stage of the project activity without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way.
- I understand that, being voluntary, I will not be paid for my participation.
- I am 18 or older

Choose your preferred option:

- I authorize the project partner(s) to use the information I share for scientific, communication and reporting purposes provided that they remain confidential and anonymity is ensured.
- I authorize the project partner(s) to use the information I share for scientific, communication and reporting purposes. Furthermore, I authorize to be quoted by mentioning my name/organization

Annex 2 – Declaration of GDPR compliance

INSTRUCTIONS

The following declaration aimed to confirm that all personal data collection and processing in the research design of the BIN2BEAN project will be carried out according to the EU and (if applicable) national legislation and requirements. The document must be signed by the Data Protection Officer (or its designated representative) of each BIN2BEAN partner. A scanned copy must be sent to the Project Coordinator, while the original signed copy must be kept on file and provided upon request to the European Commission. You can remove the instructions when printing and signing the document.

I, the undersigned, _____ as the Data Protection Officer (or its designated representative) of the BIN2BEAN project partner _____ (full name) - _____ (short name), established in _____ (full address), declares that:

- All personal data collection and processing in the research design of the BIN2BEAN project will be carried out according to the EU and national legislation.
- The original signed copy of this declaration will be kept on file.
- The organisation commits to provide this signed declaration upon request.

AND that *(choose one of the following options)*

- All additional declarations and authorizations for the lawful collection and processing of personal data as required by the national law have been completed.
- No additional declarations or authorizations for the lawful collection and processing of personal data are required by the national law.

Date

Signature

Annex 3 – Additional documents provided by LLs

AMS GDPR procedure details

The research of the Amsterdam Living Lab is coordinated by AMS Institute and executed by Bin2Bean partner Wageningen University, and Bin2Bean partner Wageningen Research. Both organizations have a common guideline on GDPR and follow the Dutch [Code of Conduct for Universities](#). For both organizations, the first step is to register the Bin2Bean project at the WUR Registration system called SmartPia. The second step is the generation of a Data Management Plan; a standard WUR-DMP can be made according the following [link](#). In case of data sharing, the following principles will be followed for [sharing](#) data.

The AMS Institute management approved to rely on the WUR GDPR guidelines and will monitor this during the project. In case AMS Institute needs to store or access data to invite and communicate with Bin2Bean stakeholders, it will store the data in a separate data storage system that can be accessed by AMS Institute team members only. The AMS Institute will follow the EU GDPR compliance guidelines as defined in the present document.

Hellenic Republic
Municipality of Egaleo
Directorate of Planning, Development & Transparency

 364 Iera Odos Str. & Kalvou, Postal Code 12243, Egaleo
 D. Tzempelikos
 tzempelikos@egaleo.gr
 www.aigaleo.gr
 213.2044841

Topic: Approval of the Ethics Committee for research with human participants in the context of the EU co-funded project “Bin2Bean” [HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-10]

It is officially announced that the Ethics Committee of the Municipality of Egaleo, located at the city of Egaleo (364 Iera Odos Str. & Kalvou, Postal Code 12243, Egaleo) gives full approval for data collection and in the context of the research procedures and activities that form part of the EU co-funded project titled “Bin2Bean” [HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-10]».

With the current document, the project partner (Municipality of Egaleo team) commits to the fact that certain rules regarding ethics in social research with human participants will be followed. More specifically:

- All the participants from Greece will provide their consent in order to participate in any data collection procedure, after they have been fully informed about the aims and objectives of the project Bin2Bean and the aims of this data collection procedure.
- The participants will have the right to withdraw from the data collection process at any time without providing any particular reason and/or justification.
- The rules and regulations of the European Union in terms of the GDPR and the protection of sensitive personal data will be followed, since research activities in the context of the project “Bin2Bean” regarding the GDPR comply with the EU and national regulations.
- The data and the information that will be collected will remain anonymous and strictly confidential, while there will be no personal identifiers based on the information participants will provide. Participants will be informed that their data will not be shared with any other parties.
- Participants' data will only be accessed by the team members of the Municipality of Egaleo that run the Bin2Bean project, and will remain safe and secure until after the completion of the project, in 2026.

- The -
Director of Planning, Development and Transparency
& Designated Representative of the Data Protection officer

DIMITRIOS
TZEMPELIKOS
28.02.2024 20:09

Dimitrios Tzempelikos

UNTERNEHMENSLEITLINIE

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

DAS GANZE SEHEN.

STADTREINIGUNG

HALTUNG ZEIGEN.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

EINORDNUNG DER UNTERNEHMENSLEITLINIE DER STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

Die Anwendung unserer Unternehmensleitlinie ist eine wichtige Voraussetzung für die Erreichung der Unternehmensziele. Diese sind aus dem Zielbild des Senates abgeleitet und werden in unserer Balanced Scorecard messbar gemacht.

Die Unternehmensleitlinie beschreibt und definiert die Erwartung an die Grundhaltung aller Mitarbeiterinnen und Mitarbeiter* unseres Unternehmens. Unsere Führungskräfte tragen als Vorbilder eine besondere Verantwortung bei der Umsetzung der Unternehmensleitlinie.

* Der Übersicht halber wird im Text die männliche Schreibweise verwendet. Selbstverständlich sind jeweils männliche und weibliche Beschäftigte gemeint.

WERTE LEBEN.

UNSERE WERTE

Wertschätzung

Ehrlichkeit

Loyalität

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

REGELN ACHTEN.

ECKPUNKTE UNSERES HANDELNS

Unser Unternehmen ist als Anstalt des öffentlichen Rechts in besonderem Maße an Gesetz und Recht gebunden. Wir erfüllen nachhaltig unsere Aufgaben unter wirtschaftlichen, umwelt- und sozialverträglichen Aspekten.

Arbeitssicherheit, Gesundheitsschutz und Umweltschutz sind zentrale Elemente unserer Unternehmensstrategie.

Wir sorgen durch unser Handeln für die Zufriedenheit unserer Kunden und zeigen eine hohe Einsatzbereitschaft bei Bedarf auch außerhalb der üblichen Arbeitszeiten.

Uns ist die Bedeutung und Wirkung unseres Handelns bewusst.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

HINSEHEN.

UNSER ARBEITSVERSTÄNDNIS

Wir wollen einen stetigen Verbesserungsprozess.

Wir stellen uns dem Vergleich mit anderen und sind bereit, von den Besten zu lernen.

Wir lernen aus unseren Fehlern.

Wir pflegen die „Kultur des Hinsehens“.

Wir schauen bei Fehlverhalten nicht weg, sondern geben Rückmeldung und ziehen angemessene Konsequenzen.

Wir wissen, dass Unfallzahlen und Krankenstand wichtige Kenngrößen zur Beurteilung und Korrektur der Arbeitsqualität einer jeden betrieblichen Einheit sind.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

MITDENKEN.

UNSER ARBEITSVERSTÄNDNIS

Wir arbeiten effektiv und sichern dadurch auch unseren Arbeitsplatz und unseren Lebensunterhalt.

Wir planen zielorientiert, wirtschaftlich und mit Weitblick.

Wir informieren uns über Veränderungen im politischen und wirtschaftlichen Umfeld.

Wir erkennen sich verändernde Bedingungen und verstehen sie als Chancen.

Wir erbringen unsere Leistungen zur Zufriedenheit unserer internen und externen Kunden.

Wir schaffen mit unseren Leistungen die Basis für positive Rahmenbedingungen und Entwicklungsmöglichkeiten.

Wir übernehmen die Verantwortung für unser Handeln, sowohl für den Erfolg als auch für den Misserfolg.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

ZIELE SETZEN.

UNSER VERSTÄNDNIS VON FÜHRUNG

Wir führen zielgerichtet, effizient und transparent anhand vereinbarter Ziele und kontrollieren Arbeitsergebnisse mit dem Ziel einer erfolgreichen Aufgabenerfüllung.

Wir führen bewusst Veränderungsprozesse durch und nehmen auch damit verbundene Unsicherheiten und Ängste ernst.

Wir leiten, steuern und entscheiden zügig, nachvollziehbar und verlässlich und geben durch unser Verhalten Orientierung.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

KLARTEXT REDEN.

UNSER VERSTÄNDNIS VON FÜHRUNG

Wir geben, suchen und bekommen umfassende Informationen, um unsere Aufgaben optimal erfüllen zu können, kommunizieren zielgerichtet auf allen Ebenen und beachten dabei zwischenmenschlich einwandfreie Umgangsformen.

Wir nehmen Personalbetreuung ernst, weil nur zufriedene, motivierte, gesunde und qualifizierte Mitarbeiter auf Dauer gute Arbeitsergebnisse erzielen.

Wir fördern kooperative Arbeitsformen und schaffen durch Lob und konstruktive Kritik den Rahmen für ein gutes Betriebsklima.

Wir schaffen Verantwortungsbewusstsein durch Delegation und nutzen die vielfältigen Potenziale unserer Mitarbeiter.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

ZUSAMMENHALT STÄRKEN.

UNSER UMGANG MITEINANDER

Wir gehen so mit unseren Kollegen, Mitarbeitern und Kunden um, wie wir es für uns selbst wünschen.

Wir schätzen einen menschlichen Umgang und begegnen uns gegenseitig mit Respekt.

Wir schaffen Vertrauen durch sachliches, transparentes und authentisches Handeln.

Wir schützen Vertrauen durch umsichtiges und diskretes Verhalten.

Wir sorgen für Transparenz in unserem Arbeitsbereich.

Wir lassen auch kritische Fragen zu, nehmen Kritik an und lernen daraus.

Wir äußern Kritik zuerst gegenüber den Betroffenen.

Wir reden miteinander, nicht übereinander.

Wir informieren ehrlich und umfassend.

Wir sind loyal und handeln zum Wohle der Stadtreinigung Hamburg (nicht nur der eigenen Abteilung oder Region).

LEISTUNG ZEIGEN.

UNSER UMGANG MIT KUNDEN

Wir sind Teil der Stadtreinigung Hamburg und prägen das Bild der Stadtreinigung Hamburg und der Stadt in der Öffentlichkeit. Wir sorgen dafür, dass das Ansehen der Stadtreinigung Hamburg einheitlich gut ist und bleibt.

Wir sind stolz darauf, bei der Stadtreinigung Hamburg zu arbeiten.

Wir prägen eine kundenfreundliche Haltung in unserer Region/Abteilung.

Wir arbeiten so, dass der Kunde unsere Leistung wertschätzt.

STADTREINIGUNG HAMBURG

Stadtreinigung Hamburg
Bullerdeich 19
20537 Hamburg

Telefon: 040 / 25760

E-Mail: info@srhh.de

Internet: www.stadtreinigung.de

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union (Grant n°.101113011) Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.